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Authors	Zhara Kahrobaee, Martin Palm
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O-TA-10**Determination of Phase Equilibria in the Ti–Al–Si System at 800–1200 °C**Zahra Kahrobaee and Martin Palm

Max-Planck-Institut für Eisenforschung GmbH, 40237 Düsseldorf, Germany, z.kahrobaee@mpie.de

Introduction

Advanced γ -TiAl based alloys are nowadays employed in the low-pressure turbine of new aircraft engines, where they have replaced Ni-base superalloys. Due to their lower density, fuel consumption and thereby the amount of emissions could be substantially reduced. However, to increase the engine operation temperature and thus overall efficiency even more, these alloys should be further improved. To reach this goal, the key properties are creep and oxidation resistance, which can be improved through tailoring of the microstructure and alloying [1]. Addition of Si is known to be beneficial in improving the creep resistance through formation of fine-scaled Ti_5Si_3 precipitates [2, 3]. Si also substantially improves the oxidation resistance through refining TiO_2 particles, which results in the formation of a more compact oxide scale and it facilitates Al diffusion in the scale, which restrains further formation of TiO_2 [4].

Efficient development of γ -TiAl based alloys relies on the knowledge of phase equilibria in dependence of temperature. CALPHAD (CALculation of PHase Diagram) modelling is a widely used method by which phase diagrams and phase transitions can be calculated. CALPHAD modelling crucially depends on the underlying database, which is based on experimental investigations. Available experimental data on phase equilibria in the Ti–Al–Si system, specifically in the Ti-rich part, are at least partially controversial. E.g., for the solid solubility of Si in γ -TiAl at 1000 °C reported data vary between 0 [5] and 3.1 at.% [6]. Also, the solid solubility for Al in Ti_5Si_3 in dependence of temperature has not been settled. However, knowledge of the solid solubility of Si in TiAl and Al in Ti_5Si_3 in dependence of temperature are essential for the design of more creep resistant γ -TiAl-based alloys, because they yield the volume fraction of Ti_5Si_3 at a certain temperature for a given composition.

Within a large-scale collaborative project, the partners Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon, Germany, Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria, MPIE, and Thermo-Calc Software AB, Sweden are improving thermodynamic data for a number of Ti–Al–X(Y) systems for the next generation of advanced CALPHAD databases for Ti–Al alloys [7]. As a part of this project, phase equilibria between the Ti–Al-rich phases and Ti_5Si_3 between 800–1200 °C are experimentally investigated and specifically the solid solubility of Si in γ -TiAl and Al in Ti_5Si_3 were established.

Materials and Methods

From high-purity elements, seven alloys have been prepared by crucible-free levitation melting or advanced arc melting. For heat-treatments at 800–1100 °C, slices of the alloys were encapsulated in high-purity quartz tubes back-filled with Ar and annealed for 165–1000 h, followed by quenching in brine. Heat-treatments at 1200 °C were performed using a double-crucible technique [8]. Heat-treatments at 1200 °C were performed for 24 h under flowing dry Ar, subsequently quenching the samples in brine. Compositions of the alloys and impurity contents in the as-cast condition and, for a couple of alloys, after heat treatment were established by wet chemical analysis. Phases were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD) at room temperature using powder. Compositions of the coexisting phases were established by electron probe microanalysis (EPMA). Phase transformation temperatures were measured on bulk samples by differential thermal analysis (DTA) by heating up to a maximum of about 1400 °C at a heating rate of 10 K/min.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 (a–e) shows the microstructure of Ti-47.4Al-9.1Si (in at.%) after annealing at 800–1200 °C. Phases were identified by XRD as illustrated in Fig. 2. Observed phases are TiAl + $TiAl_2$ + Ti_5Si_3 at 800–1100 °C and TiAl + Ti_5Si_3 at 1200 °C (Fig. 1).

The enlarged back-scattered electron (BSE) image (Fig. 1 c) shows that Ti_5Si_3 appears in two different morphologies, i.e. as large idiomorphic grains and as small spherical particles, which was also observed in most of the other investigated samples. The liquidus projection [6] shows that all alloys which contained large, idiomorphic Ti_5Si_3 are located in the field of primary crystallization of Ti_5Si_3 . EPMA of these large grains, which formed within the liquid at elevated temperatures, and the small ones, which formed during annealing, showed differences in the Al content of up to 3.5 at.%. Apparently, even annealing for 1000 h at 1000 °C is not sufficient to equilibrate the large, primary Ti_5Si_3 grains. Therefore, only small spherical Ti_5Si_3 particles were measured, which, in case of the microstructure shown in Fig. 1 c, are in contact with $TiAl_2$ and TiAl. Differences between data reported in the literature could be attributed to the aforementioned issue. E.g., the maximum solid solubility of Al in Ti_5Si_3 at 1000 °C was found to be 7.4 at.%, compared to 10.9 at.% reported previously [6]. The solid solubility of Si in γ -TiAl is about 0.8 at.% and does not change with increasing temperature.

The established partial isothermal sections in the Ti–Al–Si system will be discussed in detail in the presentation.

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Fig. 1: BSE images of Ti-47.4Al-9.1Si at.% heat-treated at temperatures 800-1200 °C.

Fig. 2: XRD profile of Ti-47.4Al-9.1Si at.% heat-treated 1000 °C/1000 h.

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